

Australian Research Data Commons

Innovation Starts with Data

Year in Review

The ARDC is enabled by NCRIS

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Acknowledgments

We acknowledge and celebrate the First Australians on whose traditional lands we live and work, and we pay our respects to Elders past and present.

We'd like to acknowledge all of our members, partners, collaborators and community for their contribution and support — the ARDC would not be possible without you.

ARDC governance

bit.ly/ardc-governance ▶

Meet our ARDC members

bit.ly/ardc-members ▶

Our People

Thank you to ARDC staff, partners, and ARDC-supported project and program team members for your contributions.

Meet our national and international partners

bit.ly/ardc-partners ▶

ARDC staff at the 2025 all staff retreat

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A Message from Our Chair

Craig Roy FAICD MBA MSc

As we reflect on another year, I am struck by the rapid pace at which transformative technologies such as artificial intelligence and advanced data analytics are evolving and the enormous potential this offers to researchers. Against this dynamic backdrop, the ARDC remains committed to delivering the necessary data infrastructure, tools and skills to Australian researchers to produce cutting-edge research, drive innovation, and improve the livelihood and wellbeing of Australians.

We've seen significant advancement in establishing project partnerships across our three Thematic Research Data Commons: People, Planet and HASS & Indigenous. These collaborations are strengthening the national research infrastructure ecosystem and creating new opportunities for cross-disciplinary innovation that address society's most pressing challenges.

Among our key highlights this year, we launched two new nodes of the Nectar Research Cloud - one in collaboration with AARNet and another at the University of Adelaide - significantly enhancing national compute capacity and driving cross-institutional collaboration. The international adoption of the ARDC-developed Research Activity Identifier (RAiD) demonstrates Australia's leadership in global research infrastructure standards. Our commitment to international collaboration was strengthened through a valuable skills exchange with the Digital Research Alliance of Canada. And with 31 member organisations, the ARDC's growing community reflects strong sector-wide support and recognition of our critical role in the Australian research ecosystem.

Looking ahead, we are making substantial progress implementing the recommendations of the National Digital Research Infrastructure Strategy, collaborating across the sector to ensure seamless access to data, digital tools and compute power, supported by a skilled workforce. We are also developing a national program to harness the power of artificial intelligence to enhance the data ecosystem, and responding to community needs by progressing secure national cloud capability to support sensitive data analysis.

These achievements position Australia at the forefront of digital research infrastructure, equipping researchers to tackle tomorrow's challenges today.

On behalf of the ARDC Board, I extend my sincere thanks to our dedicated team, our valued partners and the broader Australian research community. Your continued collaboration and support are vital to advancing digital research infrastructure that serves the national interest and drives innovation across all sectors. ■

Our commitment to international collaboration was strengthened through a valuable skills exchange with the Digital Research Alliance of Canada. And with 31 member organisations, the ARDC's growing community reflects strong sector-wide support and recognition of our critical role in the Australian research ecosystem.

Innovation starts with data, and this year has demonstrated how the ARDC's focus on driving uptake of our products and services is delivering measurable impact across Australia's research landscape. We are encouraged by the growing engagement we're seeing across a number of key platforms, including: Health Data Australia for discovering and accessing clinical trials data; Open Ecoacoustics for continental-scale ecological monitoring through acoustic analysis; and the Language Data Commons of Australia for accessing nationally significant language collections.

A Message from Our CEO

Rosie Hicks

We're committed to measuring impact and demonstrating the benefit of Australia's investment in digital research infrastructure. By tracking how researchers engage with the ARDC's products and services, we can see tangible evidence of how data-driven research is accelerating discovery and supporting world-class research outcomes and innovation. I'm pleased to share some of these case studies with you in this Year in Review.

The ARDC's future lies in harnessing technological advances to meet the evolving needs of the research community and enabling research translation and innovation. We are developing capabilities in artificial intelligence to enhance our data ecosystem, progressing our secure national cloud infrastructure to support sensitive data analysis, and exploring dataspace for collaboration with industry. Yet the balance between innovative technologies and reliability is critical - as we embrace cutting-edge technologies, we also remain committed to delivering robust and enduring digital research infrastructure that Australian researchers can rely on.

Central to the ARDC's achievements is our dedicated and knowledgeable team. The commitment, passion and deep expertise of our staff are what transform bold ideas into tangible infrastructure that empowers researchers to solve complex challenges and innovate for the benefit of all Australians.

The ARDC looks forward to continuing to contribute to Australia's vibrant research ecosystem, where innovation starts with data that is accessible, secure and ready to unlock Australia's full research potential. ■

Central to the ARDC's achievements is our dedicated and knowledgeable team. The commitment, passion and deep expertise of our staff are what transform bold ideas into tangible infrastructure that empowers researchers to solve complex challenges and innovate for the benefit of all Australians.

Delivering on the ARDC Strategy

Our Purpose

To provide Australian researchers with competitive advantage through data

Our Mission

To accelerate research and innovation by driving excellence in the creation, analysis and retention of high-quality data assets

Our Strategy

The ARDC delivers leading-edge digital research infrastructure that empowers Australian researchers to tackle society's greatest challenges. Our strategy is shaped by national priorities and extensive consultation with the research community, ensuring our initiatives are aligned with the evolving needs of academia, government and industry.

We are building and sustaining 3 **Thematic Research Data Commons** in partnership with research, industry and government. These are supported by our underpinning infrastructure: the **ARDC Nectar Research Cloud**, **National Information Infrastructure** and a coordinated national approach to **digital research skills development**.

We drive the adoption of the innovative services and standards that we are creating in these partnerships across all fields of research, and ensure researchers have the skills to use these emerging technologies.

Together, we are building a national knowledge infrastructure that transforms data into innovation, and research into real-world solutions.

Image - Gorodenkoff / stock.adobe

Image - themorningglory / stock.adobe

Image - marlo-pursic / unsplash.com

Strategic Drivers

Underpinning Activities

ARDC in Numbers

PEOPLE

Research Data Commons

Health Data Australia

712

users generated
2.4k views across
the Health Data
Australia platform

72

organisations
participating in Health
Data Australia across
9 nodes

PLANET

Research Data Commons

Open Ecoacoustics

1.7k

total users

2.5M

records added

7.2M

records downloaded

HASS & INDIGENOUS

Research Data Commons

Language Data Commons (LDaCA)

5.6k

LDaCA Data Portal
active users

1k

LDaCA
BinderHub users

Language Data Analysis Laboratory (LADAL)

229k

LADAL website
page views

ARDC NECTAR RESEARCH CLOUD

3.9k

unique users of Nectar services (Research Cloud, Virtual Desktop, Jupyter Notebook and Binderhub services) from

- 15 NCRIS facilities
- 11 ARC Centres of Excellence
- 37 Australian universities

1.9k

research projects used Nectar, of which 277 were ARC / NHMRC / MRFF grants

667M

virtual CPU hours used

NATIONAL INFORMATION INFRASTRUCTURE

Digital Object Identifier (DOI) service

81

research organisations issuing DOIs

235k

DOIs minted in the year

- 19.6k monthly average
- 1m DOIs in total

Research Activity Identifiers (RAiD) service

300

RAiDs minted

FOOD SECURITY Research Data Challenges

9

Projects completed

- 1 in progress
- totalling \$11.9M
- co-investment ratio of 1:1.5

Isotopes.au

865k

records in total

- 6.1k visits to platform
- 869 searches of data
- 48 data downloads

SKILLS

21

ARDC-led training events

- Nectar Research Cloud training, HASS & Indigenous RDC Summer School
- 850 participants in total

Digital Research Skills Australasia (DReSA) national training registry

875

new training events added

2.5k

accumulated training events

People Research Data Commons

National digital infrastructure for health and medical research

Health data in Australia spans many sectors, jurisdictions and types. Due to its sensitive nature, research using health data must comply with privacy, ethical and regulatory standards. For Australian health research and translation to be seamless and secure and deliver benefits across the boundaries of organisations, sectors and jurisdictions, national digital infrastructure is crucial.

Through the People Research Data Common (People RDC), we're delivering national infrastructure to address 4 research data challenges with partners from across the Australian health system, building the social and technical bridges to develop connected infrastructure:

1 Data Strategy and Discovery

We're making health research data more findable, accessible, reusable and interoperable (FAIR) by:

- a improving data access and sharing for clinical research and cohort studies through Health Data Australia, a national catalogue of health data established in 2023 in partnership with 72 institutions
- b working with other NCRIS facilities on consistent data collection, curation and access standards across national genomic, phenomic, imaging, microscopy, population health and nuclear medicine data collections

2 Secure Data Access

We've developed a framework for Trusted Research Environments, established a national community of practice and are deploying a network of secure access services for analysing health studies research data

3 Data Integration

We've established a national framework and alliance that will help improve and save lives by joining up health data nationally through common data models, ontologies and identifiers

4 Advanced Analytics in Healthcare

We've developed a framework and pathfinder, and are developing a reference architecture and roadmap for AI-enabled health analytics infrastructure. We're also advancing federated machine learning and building an AI resource hub for healthcare research

While building national capabilities through these activities, we're also addressing data challenges specific to cancer and infectious disease research through our Disease Data Challenges program, part of the ARDC's Translational Research Data Challenges initiative.

Access resources for health and medical researchers

bit.ly/ardc-people-res

Be part of the People Research Data Commons

bit.ly/ardc-people

Simplifying Consent for Health and Medical Research

A new, simplified participant information and consent form (PICF) template is set to improve how participants engage with health and medical research studies in Australia, and enable data sharing to improve Australians' health through research.

For ethical health research, including clinical trials, people need information to help them decide whether to participate in a study. With the global shift towards sharing clinical trial data for better health outcomes, obtaining participant consent to share data at the outset of the trial is critical to ensuring transparency and respecting autonomy. However, most of the sector uses PICF templates created over a decade ago that are often long, complex, and difficult to understand.

Image - suwano / stockadobe

If you've got a 30-page document, it's a genuine barrier to being involved in clinical trials and health research. This project will have a beneficial impact on the community through better communication, which is crucial to healthcare in the modern era.

Simon Windsor,
Manager of Research Governance and Ethics,
SA Health's Southern Adelaide Local Health Network (SALHN)

Learn more about the project

bit.ly/data-sharing-frameworks ▶

CT:IQ (Clinical Trials: Impact & Quality), in partnership with the ARDC through the People Research Data Commons and our partners contributing to Health Data Australia, has created a simpler, shorter and more engaging PICF template for Australian health and medical research. The new participant-centric template was designed by a multidisciplinary project team – including consumers, researchers, contract research organisations and human research ethics committees – with input from over 700 survey respondents.

The simplified PICF template is free for researchers to access and modify and is accompanied by a comprehensive user guide. It helps potential participants make better-informed decisions about research participation and future sharing of their research data. For researchers, the template facilitates clarity and certainty about data sharing, enabling them to ethically share data via Health Data Australia to improve lives through accelerated health research.

The template has received support from state governments, highlighting its potential to inform standards nationally.

Following the successful beta-testing phase, the project is seeking endorsement from the National Health and Medical Research Council to replace the existing PICF templates. Simplifying PICFs is a promising shift towards more accessible, participant-friendly approaches in health and medical research, reducing barriers to informed consent and appropriate data reuse. ■

Image - photofrizz / stock-adobe

Planet Research Data Commons

National data infrastructure for earth and environmental science research

Earth and environmental science tackles complex challenges like climate change, ecosystem deterioration and energy transition. Collaboration across domains and sectors is essential for research and decision-making, and reliable data and information supply chains are crucial to delivering connected, high-quality data, and data processing, analysis and decision making tools.

To facilitate the sharing and reuse of data, workflows and analytic methods, the Planet Research Data Commons (Planet RDC) provides national-scale data infrastructure for environmental and earth science researchers, policy makers and decision makers in 4 focus areas:

The ARDC is also building a national dataspace capability to create trusted ecosystems for secure data exchange between research, industry and government. Three dataspaces are being piloted.

Be part of the Planet Research Data Commons
bit.ly/ardc-planet

Access resources for earth and environmental researchers
bit.ly/ardc-planet-res

The EcoCommons team.

Image - Marc Grimwade / ARDC

Image - ARDC / Rob Milne

1 Trusted Environmental Data and Information Supply Chains

Supporting sound scientific conclusions and decisions, and lowering data sharing costs. Exemplar regions include the Pilbara and Cockburn Sound in WA, Gayini in NSW and the Gippsland Offshore Renewable Energy declared area in Victoria.

2 Integrated FAIR Datasets and Services

Bringing together disparate data and preparing it for analysis to support research and national reporting requirements. Projects include:

- a. creating data portals for National Environmental Science Program (NESP) hubs and the Australian Plant Phenomics Network (APPN)
- b. enhancing national-scale integrated datasets and services, such as AusTraits
- c. providing data infrastructure and coordination to enable robust, repeatable ecosystem and biodiversity indicators via the Environmental Indicators Initiative.

3 Planet Infrastructure (Networked Modelling, Analytics and Decision Support)

Enabling cross-sectoral and multi-disciplinary collaboration. Projects include:

- a. enhancing the EcoCommons, Biosecurity Commons and Open Ecoacoustics research platforms
- b. establishing the Wildlife Observatory of Australia (WildObs), national infrastructure for processing and sharing wildlife camera data.

4 Governance of Indigenous Data, and Skills

Underpinning the first 3 focus areas.

Image - Rob Mullaly

NSW National Parks and Wildlife Service is deploying acoustic recorders to track the changing health of national parks.

Using the Power of Sound to Monitor Australia's Biodiversity

ARDC-supported Open Ecoacoustics is helping researchers listen to the land to preserve Australia's native animals and ecosystems.

Australia's bushland has a voice. Every chirp, croak and howl tells a story about our native wildlife, a rich source of information about the health of our ecosystems. Now, scientists are turning to acoustic monitoring as a powerful tool for understanding ecosystem health.

Networks of sound recorders have been deployed across Australia to capture environmental sounds. They help researchers detect pests, monitor changes in wildlife populations, and assess ecosystem dynamics. However, managing and analysing this large volume of data is a significant challenge.

Open Ecoacoustics is a platform that helps understand environmental changes through big data, allowing for informed environmental management decisions.

In partnership with the ARDC's Planet Research Data Commons, Open Ecoacoustics provides open access to data, technologies, methods and standards for monitoring threatened species and ecosystems on a continental scale. It is also delivering powerful tools to process and analyse vast amounts of acoustic data, including AI sound recognisers, running on the ARDC Nectar Research Cloud. This ensures acoustic monitoring data is easy to process, interoperable and reusable to maximise its impact. The platform delivers data and analysis that helps inform management actions for over 30 partners across government, industry and the private sector.

The NSW National Parks and Wildlife Service uses Open Ecoacoustics in its Ecological Health Performance Scorecards program to track the changing health of NSW national parks, providing important information about native plants, animals and natural resources.

Open Ecoacoustics plays an important role in analysing and storing the collected acoustic data. The program has already discovered that some species, including the Eastern pygmy possum, are more abundant than previously thought.

Open Ecoacoustics is part of the ARDC's Machine Observation Data Processing Infrastructure program, which is establishing shared infrastructure, services and standards to enable ecoacoustic and camera trap data processing. Together with WildObs, a platform for storing and processing camera trap images, the program is set to accelerate environmental monitoring research in Australia. ■

The ecoacoustic data itself is useful for increasing knowledge on species across the state, which contributes to threatened species management and assessments. From the public's perspective, it's also about increasing confidence that we're managing our parks effectively and being transparent about what actions we are taking to make them even better.

Danielle Stokeld,
Manager of the Ecological Health Unit,
NSW National Parks and Wildlife Service

Learn more about the Machine Observation Data Processing Infrastructure program

bit.ly/ardc-mods ▶

Image - Marc Grimwade / ARDC

Robert McLellan from the Language Data Commons of Australia presenting at the ARDC Indigenous Data Masterclass in February 2025.

Image - Marc Grimwade / ARDC

Uncle Michael Williams (rightmost) leading a yarning circle at the ARDC HASS & Indigenous RDC Summer School.

HASS & Indigenous Research Data Commons

Powering data-driven research on Australia's history, culture and heritage

In collaboration with Indigenous Australians, the research community, industry and government, the Humanities, Arts, Social Sciences and Indigenous Research Data Commons (HASS & Indigenous RDC) is harnessing research data to enhance Australian social and cultural wellbeing and help understand and preserve our culture, history and heritage.

The RDC is delivering new digital platforms and data directories that help discover and access Australia's rich HASS and Indigenous data and innovative analysis tools. The RDC is also upskilling researchers to use data-driven approaches in HASS research and apply Indigenous data governance principles.

The HASS & Indigenous RDC has achieved joint resourcing of more than \$52 million over the coming 4 years in partnership with research institutions, government and non-governmental organisations. It is delivering infrastructure in 6 areas:

Be part of the HASS & Indigenous Research Data Commons

bit.ly/ardc-hass ▶

Access resources for HASS and Indigenous researchers

bit.ly/ardc-hass-res ▶

1 Improving Indigenous Research Capabilities

Building an Aboriginal and Torres Strait Islander Research Data Commons.

2 Language Data Commons of Australia

Ensuring long-term access to nationally significant language collections.

3 Social Science Research Infrastructure Network

Social Science infrastructure for research that contributes to a more equitable and resilient society.

4 Connections

a. **ARDC Community Data Lab**
Tools for researchers to use data from galleries, libraries, archives, museums and other collections.

b. **Annual Summer School**
An annual event for researchers and Indigenous data custodians to learn digital research skills.

5 Australian Internet Observatory

Research infrastructure for social data and digital platforms.

6 Australian Creative Histories and Futures

Making Australia's rich history in the arts more accessible.

Image - Marc Grimwade / ARDC

ARDC Indigenous Data Governance Masterclass participants interacting with Indigenous materials during a tour of the Queensland Memory Collection of the State Library of Queensland.

Arne ingkerreke apurtelhe-ileme

A new collection brings together the incredible life's work of Veronica Perrurle Dobson AM.

In April 2025, the Centre for Australian Languages and Linguistics (CALL) at Batchelor Institute launched Arne ingkerreke apurtelhe-ileme (Gathering all the things together) at its Mparntwe (Alice Springs) campus. The project is a partnership with the ARDC-supported Language Data Commons of Australia (LDaCA), which provides digital infrastructure to ensure the long-term care of nationally significant language data.

Veronica Perrurle Dobson AM is an Eastern Arrernte elder, linguist, educator, author and ecologist, whose advocacy and work for language and culture are widely recognised and deeply respected. For over 4 decades, Veronica has worked in many interrelated fields – language documentation and teaching, lexicography, interpreting, ethnobiology and land management. A guide to her life, work and publications is now showcased through Arne ingkerreke apurtelhe-ileme on veronicadobson.au.

For me, what I have done has not been like work. I do what I do because I love my language and know how important it is – this is the knowledge I learned from my grandparents.

Veronica Dobson AM, Eastern Arrernte elder,
linguist, educator, author and ecologist

Veronica Perrurle Dobson AM

Learn more about the Language
Data Commons of Australia (LDaCA)

ldaca.edu.au ▶

Image - Charlee-Anne Ah Chee

Arne ingkerreke apurtelhe-ileme project team (from left): Angela Harrison (*Batchelor Institute*), Camille Dobson (*Batchelor Institute*), Veronica Dobson, Jennifer Green (*The University of Melbourne*), Ben Foley (*The University of Queensland and Language Data Commons of Australia*).

Veronica's daughter, Camille Dobson, spoke about creating the collection at the launch.

"Over the past year, I was privileged to work with Ben Foley, Jennifer Green and Ange Harrison on this project, which places the Aboriginal knowledge holder at the centre of the collection. It is an important collection and now means that her amazing work can be found in one place," she said.

Dr Jennifer Green, Postdoctoral Fellow in Australian Sign Languages at the University of Melbourne, said, "We hope that the arne ingkerreke apurtelhe-ileme website is the first of many that focus attention on the enormous contributions made by First Nations peoples to archival collections. Plans are already underway to use the methodologies we developed to make another website that provides a guide to the language work of Anmatyerr women April Pengart Campbell, Eileen Pwerrerl Campbell and Clarrie Kemarr Long from Ti Tree community in Central Australia. Access to and sustainability of collections such as these is crucial to their ongoing relevance in supporting community projects."

Veronica's intention for Arne ingkerreke apurtelhe-ileme is that the fruits of her work are cared for and accessible to future generations. For Camille, the collection also has the potential to inspire.

"Still working at 80, Mum is an inspiration to our family. I hope others will also be inspired by her passion, dedication and story," she said. ■

ARDC Nectar Research Cloud

Providing fast, remote access to computational software and data to Australian researchers

The ARDC Nectar Research Cloud is Australia’s national cloud research computing service. Fast, interactive and self-service, Nectar allows Australian researchers to remotely access computational resources, software and data at no cost with ongoing, tailored support. It makes it easy to collaborate on research projects nationally and internationally. Nectar also powers the ARDC’s other national cloud computing services, and hundreds of research platforms and tools for ARDC partners.

In the past year, 2 new nodes of Nectar have launched at AARNet and the University of Adelaide, enhancing cross-institutional collaboration and research.

Get started with the ARDC Nectar Research Cloud and services

bit.ly/ardc-nectar

More ARDC cloud computing services, powered by Nectar

A wide range of specialised, national services are available via Nectar to save time, boost productivity, facilitate collaboration and power groundbreaking research.

Virtual Desktop Service

Access an extra personal computer in the cloud with the operating system and useful apps pre-installed. It’s a simple way to use Nectar compute resources.

Jupyter Notebook Service

Develop, combine and export code and computational output with formatted, interactive explanatory text and multimedia in pre-configured environments, such as Python, R and SciPy.

BinderHub Service

Make code repositories shareable, executable and reproducible.

National GPU Service

Access GPUs and large-memory virtual machines on Nectar for demanding research activities like processing large datasets, 3D imaging, machine learning and computational modelling. This year, we launched our new AI-Ready application, which makes it easier for researchers from all disciplines to use Nectar GPUs for AI and machine learning without extensive coding and IT knowledge.

Preemptible Instances

Access extra computational power on Nectar for a short time on demand.

Image - arfhratoz2205 / stock.adobe

Image - L-Gully / ARDC

Julius Roberts, from the Nectar node at the University of Tasmania, at a Nectar Tech and Ops meeting.

Image - Kausnik Ramesh / ARDC

Professor Michael Goodsite (left), Ben Chiu and Dr Stephen Love at the ARDC Nectar Research Cloud Showcase at the University of Adelaide in February 2025.

Image - Seb / stock.adobe

Important community decisions can only be made if there's useful data. We report what people are doing on beaches in what number, so councils can plan for the future. We've been using Nectar for the modelling and AI that gives us that information, which is important because the AI training requires a lot of computing power.

Professor Rod Connolly,
Director, Coastal and Marine Research Centre, Griffith University

Image - Herrera et al 2024

Making Beach Management in Australia Smarter

Combining the power of drones, AI and the ARDC Nectar Research Cloud, researchers are gaining insights into Australian beach usage that inform coastal management.

Australia's beaches are thriving with activity – from surfing on the ocean to jogging on the sand – making them an important recreational and economic asset. Estimating the number of people using these natural spaces, and understanding how they use them, is key to maintaining the infrastructure and public safety.

Using Nectar, researchers from Griffith University, in collaboration with the City of Gold Coast, have gained new insights into the use of some of the most iconic Australian beaches and paved the way for smarter coastal management in Australia.

Led by Professor Rod Connolly, Director of Griffith University's Coastal and Marine Research Centre, the team captured drone footage of 29 Gold Coast beaches through 500 surveys and stored it on Nectar. With the GPUs on Nectar, they then ran AI algorithms repurposed from FishID, a tool developed in collaboration with the ARDC to identify, count and measure aquatic animals and plants, to count beachgoers and categorise their activities.

The team estimated that there were about 34 million visitors to the Gold Coast beaches between 2022 and 2023, about twice the number estimated by traditional headcounts. The findings prompted the City Council to increase patrols and help better allocate funds for beach management.

This smarter approach – combining the power of drones, AI and Nectar – is poised to be applied to other waters on the Gold Coast, contributing to informed, data-driven decisions for managing Australia's coastline. ■

Read the case study

bit.ly/beach-management ▶

Image - Herrera et al 2024

Researchers used AI to categorise activities of beachgoers, such as walking, resting, or swimming, with 90% accuracy.

Image - PHOTOFEST / ARDC

Dr Mingfang Wu, Product Manager, ARDC, speaking at the launch of Research Link Australia.

Image - Natasha Simons / ARDC

Joy Owango, Founder of the Training Centre in Communication (TCC-Africa), speaking at PIDfest 2024 in Prague. The ARDC and the TCC-Africa have signed an MOU to collaborate on Persistent Identifiers.

National Information Infrastructure

Research data and information services for Australia

To accelerate research and underpin research integrity, the ARDC provides high-value, contemporary and enduring national services at no cost for data discovery, linkage and interoperability.

Learn more about our research data and information services

bit.ly/ardc-services ▶

ARDC Research Data Australia

A catalogue of research data held by Australian research institutions. Researchers can contribute, find, access, and reuse data and related materials sourced from over 100 research organisations, government agencies and cultural institutions in Australia.

ARDC Research Vocabularies Australia

A service for creating, managing, finding and accessing community vocabularies, which make the meaning of research data explicit and consistent, and enhance data discoverability and interoperability.

Research Link Australia

A service for finding information on Australian research and innovation partners, activities and investments. Research, industry and government can discover and learn about opportunities for collaboration that support research translation.

Health Data Australia

A catalogue of Australian health data. Search for and request access to clinical trials datasets collected across Australia by universities, medical research institutes, clinical trials networks and health services.

Persistent Identifier (PID) Services

For Australian research organisations to support researchers with citation and attribution of their research. Our PID services are offered in partnership with international providers to connect researchers and their data, projects and institutions into the global knowledge base. We provide 4 international-standard PID services: Digital Object Identifier (DOI), Handles, International Generic Sample Number (IGSN) and Research Activity Identifier (RAiD). These identifiers may be linked to a researcher's ORCID record.

RAiD Transformation: How an Australian Idea Is Being Adopted Globally for Research Projects

In a world where research is increasingly collaborative, complex and global, an Australian innovation is helping to bring clarity and connection. RAiD – the Research Activity Identifier – is transforming how research projects are tracked, linked and understood.

Developed by the ARDC, RAiD brings together all the different components of a research project (including people, institutions, funding, instruments, software and outputs) under one unique traceable digital identifier.

Governed by ISO 23527:2022, RAiD is the only international project identifier of its kind, and its adoption is accelerating worldwide. In the United States, a National Science Foundation grant is supporting the San Diego Supercomputer Center and Lyrasis to pilot the first RAiD Registration Agency in the US. In Africa, RAiD will be integrated into the DOCiD system through a partnership with the Training Centre in Communication Africa (TCC-Africa), with a focus on Indigenous knowledge and digital patent containers. In Europe, RAiD is being embedded into the European Open Science Cloud through a collaboration with SURF in the Netherlands, with pilot projects also underway in Finland and Germany. The Czech Republic Research and Development Council has recommended the use of RAiD for research projects.

The ARDC enthusiastically supports the establishment of a RAiD Registration Agency for the US. As the global RAiD Registration Authority, we are committed to the timely rollout of RAiD for all eligible users worldwide. This is a milestone in expanding RAiD into a global service as the international standard for research project identification and tracking.

Natasha Simons,
Director, National Coordination,
Australian Research Data Commons

Image - Natasha Simons / ARDC

Professor Shawn Ross, product manager for RAiD at the ARDC, addressing international audiences about RAiD at PIDfest in Prague, 2024.

Read the article

bit.ly/raid-global ▶

The global DOI giant DataCite, with its 64 member countries, has partnered with the ARDC to provide identifiers for RAiD – a core component of the RAiD infrastructure. The ARDC has also partnered with ORCID to allow researchers to verify their identity as contributors to a RAiD, and automatically update their ORCID to reflect their participation in RAiDs.

RAiD fills a critical gap in the research ecosystem by offering a project-level identifier that enhances discoverability, reduces duplication and errors and supports better data management. A recent report found that using persistent identifiers including RAiD could save Australian researchers \$24 million and 38,000 person-days (the amount of work that one person can complete in a standard workday) annually.

As RAiD continues to expand, it demonstrates ARDC's leadership in building globally interoperable research infrastructure and its vision for a more connected research future. ■

Accelerating Research Translation

Driving faster, more effective research translation by developing national-scale human and technical infrastructure that supports the discovery, access and reuse of research outputs

By working with partners on FAIR-compliant data infrastructure and foundational tools and services, the ARDC removes collaboration barriers across research, industry and government, accelerating effective translation of knowledge into impact.

Through strategic, cross-disciplinary partnerships, the ARDC co-designs digital solutions embedded in real-world practices. Our bushfire-focused projects, for example, have delivered a national bushfire history dataset and a platform for predicting bushfire behaviour – advancing research nationally and internationally. These tools are now informing infrastructure planning, hospital capacity assessments and emergency resource deployment across industry and government.

The bushfire projects exemplify the ARDC's **Translational Research Data Challenges** approach: tackling pressing societal problems by identifying data barriers and co-developing national-scale infrastructure to enable access, analysis, and reuse across technologies, organisations and sectors.

Learn more about Translational Research Data Challenges
bit.ly/ardc-translational

Learn more about Research Link Australia
bit.ly/ardc-rla

If we make information more readily available, that means research can be more targeted, have greater impact, and be done more quickly and efficiently.

Kyaw Kyaw Soe Hlaing,
General Manager, ICT and Digitalisation,
Fisheries Research and Development Corporation

Building on the success of the bushfire initiative, the ARDC launched Food Security Data Challenges in 2022 to strengthen research into Australia's food production, consumption and distribution. Informed by extensive consultation with research, government and industry stakeholders, the program delivered a portfolio of 10 projects. Outputs include a digital data-sharing agreement tool that helps farmers retain control of their data, a traceability platform for verifying the legality and origin of mud crab catches, and a national map supporting food relief agencies in identifying underserved communities.

In 2025, the ARDC launched the third Translational Research Data Challenges initiative, Disease Data Challenges, focused on addressing data challenges specific to cancer and infectious disease research.

Building stronger links between research and industry is another focus of the ARDC. Australia has a world-class research sector and strong public investment in research and development, yet its connection to industry remains limited, particularly for small and medium-sized enterprises (SMEs), which comprise 98% of Australian businesses. SMEs often struggle to access expertise to drive innovation and growth. To address this gap, the ARDC established **Research Link Australia (RLA)** a national platform that helps businesses find relevant research expertise, fostering collaboration, commercialisation and real-world impact.

Making Waves in Fisheries and Aquaculture Research with Research Link Australia

A collaboration between the ARDC and the Fisheries Research and Development Corporation (FRDC) is making valuable fisheries research easier to find with Research Link Australia.

Over the past 30 years, FRDC has funded more than 5,000 research projects, generating insights that informed sustainable fisheries practices, management and marine conservation. However, the impact of this research depends on how easily it can be found and used. When information is hard to access, valuable findings go unused, research is duplicated and scientific progress slows.

“If we make information more readily available, research can be more targeted, have greater impact, and be done more quickly and efficiently,” said Kyaw Kyaw Soe Hlaing, FRDC’s General Manager of ICT and Digitalisation.

Addressing this challenge requires a system that connects and shares research, not just stores it. This is where the ARDC Research Link Australia (RLA) platform comes in, providing comprehensive information on Australia’s innovation ecosystem, linking researchers, organisations and outputs across sectors.

Read the case study

bit.ly/rla-frdc

Through the ARDC-FRDC project, thousands of FRDC-funded projects have been incorporated into RLA. By making data from FRDC-funded projects available alongside information from other universities and research organisations, the project is lowering barriers to access and painting a more complete picture of fisheries and aquaculture research across Australia.

The project shows what’s possible when research isn’t just collected, but connected. It serves as a model for other Research Development Corporations seeking to unlock the full value of their investments. ■

Harnessing Isotopic Data to Secure Australia’s Food Future

Isotopes.au is a new national resource that brings together isotopic data – food’s unique fingerprint – into a single, open-access resource.

Developed by CSIRO in partnership with the ARDC, Geoscience Australia, ANSTO, and the National Measurement Institute, it supports provenance verification, sustainability tracking, and biosecurity across food, water and forensic sectors. The platform enables identification of where food was grown and the environmental inputs involved, such as water use and carbon emissions. It allows data custodians to retain sovereignty while ensuring long-term data utility and balancing commercial and scientific outcomes.

Dr Nina Welti, Senior Research Scientist at CSIRO and Isotopes.au project lead, said, “Isotopes.au is capturing Australia’s wealth of isotopic data into one place to help industries demonstrate how they’re meeting environmental targets for greater transparency with trading partners and consumers.”

As the world’s first federated isotopic data platform, Isotopes.au sets a precedent for future government data-sharing initiatives under the Data Availability and Transparency Act 2022 and has accelerated planning for a national hydrogeochemistry platform. ■

Dr Nina Welti, CSIRO’s trusted supply chains expert, who leads Isotopes.au.

Learn more about IsotopesAU

isotopes.au

Digital Research Skills

Building a highly skilled digital research workforce

Research communities need a breadth of skills from foundational to advanced to use and manipulate data to its full potential. The ARDC provides national coordination of digital research skills in collaboration with research communities, institutions and infrastructure providers. This supports Australian researchers to effectively access, use and develop research data infrastructure, enabling research excellence.

This approach to digital research skills is now being recognised internationally. We are working with our Canadian and European counterparts, who are keen to adopt and implement the ARDC's Digital Research Capabilities and Skills Framework, while also sharing developments on other initiatives, such as Digital Research Skills Australasia (DReSA), which builds on technology originally developed by our European colleagues.

Run in partnership with Pawsey Supercomputing Research Centre and the National Computational Infrastructure (NCI), DReSA is an open online registry for researchers to discover digital research training events, materials, providers and trainers in Australia and New Zealand. DReSA continued to grow this year and now lists a back catalogue of 2,538 training events, over 200 current events, and 287 unique training materials on digital research skills.

Image - Marc Grimwade / ARDC

Liz Stokes, Skills Development Lead (Trainer and Research Communities), ARDC, speaking at the 2025 ARDC HASS & Indigenous Research Data Commons Summer School.

Learn more about our national leadership in digital research skills
bit.ly/ardc-skills

How the ARDC Digital Research Capabilities and Skills Framework Is Organised

Image - Marc Grimwade / ARDC

Kit Greenhill, Skills Development Lead (HASS & Indigenous), ARDC, speaking at the 2025 ARDC HASS & Indigenous Research Data Commons Summer School.

Australia and Canada Team Up to Strengthen Digital Research Infrastructure Skills

The ARDC and the Digital Research Alliance of Canada (the Alliance) have partnered to share expertise for the promotion, development and use of digital research infrastructure to advance progress in the global research ecosystem.

In February 2025, the new partnership was formalised in Sydney where the ARDC's Deputy CEO Dr Adrian Burton and the Alliance's CEO George Ross signed a memorandum of understanding. The Honourable Mary Ng, Canada's Minister of Export Promotion, International Trade and Economic Development of Canada served as a witness for Canada.

The agreement is enabling knowledge exchange and sharing between the 2 countries. Ongoing collaboration will build on existing skills initiatives. This will ultimately lead to the co-development of future skills building activities and training curriculum for the benefit of researchers and digital research infrastructure professionals in both countries.

A 2-year skills development and knowledge exchange program is now underway via a staff exchange program. The Alliance and ARDC are working on 3 priority areas: advancing training discovery and accessibility; developing learning pathways; and defining consistent evaluation methods. Both organisations will use the acquired knowledge to design and implement more robust learning pathways and frameworks that equip researchers with skills to harness the digital research infrastructure provided by each organisation. The Alliance is eager to build on the ARDC Digital Research Capabilities and Skills Framework and test it in the Canadian setting. Both organisations will share their experiences around developing national digital skills registries, exchange plans for future enhancements, and co-develop adaptable governance and sustainability strategies.

This 'digital-first' diplomatic initiative supports the development of strong research ties between the 2 countries and is an important part of the Government of Canada's Indo-Pacific Strategy.

"This represents a critical step toward advancing digital research infrastructure and strengthening international scientific collaboration," said the Honourable François-Philippe Champagne, Canadian Minister of Innovation, Science, and Industry. ■

Stephen Wu (Director, Partnerships, Digital Research Alliance of Canada), George Ross (CEO, Digital Research Alliance of Canada), The Honourable Mary Ng (Canada's Minister of Export Promotion, International Trade and Economic Development of Canada), Dr Adrian Burton (Deputy CEO, ARDC), and Keith Russell (Director, Outreach, ARDC), at the signing of the MOU in February 2025.

[Read the article](#)

bit.ly/ardc-canada ▶

By sharing expertise and knowledge, Canada and Australia are positioned to maintain our leadership in global innovation, ensuring researchers have access to cutting-edge tools and can develop the skills they need to succeed. Our collaborative approach underscores the importance of international partnerships in driving digital research innovation.

The Honourable François-Philippe Champagne, Canadian Minister of Innovation, Science and Industry

